

Getting to the End Zone: Scoring a Touchdown Through Collaborative Learning in Online Sports PR Instruction

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The Course

Public Relations in Sports is a 3000-level undergraduate course that focuses on using public relations techniques and tactics to develop beneficial relationships with stakeholders and publics on behalf of sports organizations. Topics include integrating public relations with strategic management; combining print, broadcast, online, and social media with non-traditional tactics, such as newsjacking and guerrilla marketing, to create effective public relations campaigns. The course also emphasizes crisis management techniques and corporate social responsibility.

The syllabus describes the class as a football game and introduces the appropriate lexicon. Students are players; the instructor is the head coach. Learning objectives are the game plan. The text is known as the playbook, while the modules are called strategies. Individual assessments are the statistics; they are part of the overall assessment known as the box score. Assignments and graded activities are listed on the scoreboard, which includes weekly content quizzes, or Field Goals, and the collaborative

class activity, known as the Touchdown Project. The Touchdown Project is divided into eight group assignments known as First Downs; each First Down assignment includes a collaborative group discussion called a Huddle.

By design, this course is available online only. The online learning platform is Canvas. Huddles (group discussions) make liberal use of the Canvas discussion forum. Smaller work groups known as squads sometimes meet via Zoom based on the players' convenience and preference. However, because the course is asynchronous, squad Zoom meetings are optional.

Objective

One of the key objectives in the game plan is for players to be able to articulate appropriate applications of print, broadcast, online, and social media to public relations tactics, and to combine those tactics with non-traditional tactics (newsjacking, guerrilla marketing, etc.) in development of effective public relations campaigns on behalf of clients and sports organizations. Public relations practitioners

frequently collaborate as members of teams or groups assigned to conceive and execute campaigns and the tactics that drive them. Often, campaign teams work remotely; it is not uncommon for practitioners to live and work in different states. This course engages students in collaborative, hands-on learning; the Touchdown Project is designed to require the students to work together in a remote setting to apply the curriculum to a real-world challenge: a major sports public relations campaign.

Theoretical Rationale

Research suggests that collaborative learning and engagement are essential to effective teaching of hands-on skills in diverse fields, including visual design (Coorey, 2022), language acquisition (Ujhelyi-Wojciechowski, 2022; Barth, 1999), and public relations (Coombs & Rybacki, 1999; Fraustino, Briones, & Janoske, 2015; Moore, 2014). While collaborative learning and engagement are similar, there are key differences. Laal and Laal (2012) defined collaborative learning as education involving “groups of learners working together to solve a problem, complete a task, or create a product” (p. 491). As such, collaborative learning is interactive (Moore, 2014). Finn and Zimmer (2012) argue that engagement goes beyond collaborative learning; engaged students cooperate, but they are also tasked with self-direction and self-governance in collaborative projects.

Smallwood and Brunner (2017) wrote that, when instructors combine collaborative learning with engagement in group projects that emulate real-world application of knowledge and skills, they work alongside students; however, they also encourage and compel students to be active participants by delegating responsibility for decision-making. Within reason, they allow students to make and learn from their mistakes. Ujhelyi-Wojciechowski (2022) recommended that teachers serve as facilitators by creating conditions that ensure balanced participation and mutual respect, listening to ideas from engaged, collaborative learners, and guiding students in their reflections and choices. In this vein, Barth (1999) wrote that faculty must become “le médiateur entre l’élève et le domaine des savoirs” — the mediator between the student and the domain of knowledge (p. 55).

Blumenfeld et al. (2016) argued that the way groups are organized has a significant effect on the efficacy of their work. Other factors include the tasks themselves, learner participation, and accountability measures. Instructors, they wrote, “must consider the purposes in designing group work and address potential problems of process if group work is to be successful” (p. 37).

Fostering collaboration and engagement is more challenging when courses are taught entirely online. Moore (2014) argued that the need for collaboration and engagement is more pronounced in online public relations courses because the nature of the profession requires hands-on training and experience, as well as independent thought.

The Touchdown Project

The group assignment that serves as the term paper in this course is a realistic public relations campaign aimed at promoting an underdog candidate, Southern Utah quarterback Tyson Justice, for the Heisman Trophy. In reality, of course, there is no Tyson Justice. However, he is based on a former SUU quarterback who allowed his likeness and image to be used for the campaign. Using images and game film supplied by the sports marketing arm of the SUU Athletics Department, the instructor brought Tyson to life by creating realistic media resources, such as newspaper and magazine articles, video highlights, radio interviews, and press releases. In addition, a contrived media-guide profile provides personal information, annual and career statistics, career highlights, honors and awards, etc. Although the campaign team is aware that Tyson is a fictitious person, every effort has been made to humanize him by as a standout athlete, a superior football player, an excellent student-athlete, and the epitome of a kind, considerate, moral person.

When Tyson is introduced to the class, players are instructed to consider themselves employees of Excelsior Group, a fictitious Las Vegas sports marketing and public relations firm, and that they will work under the direction of Jim Naziam, Vice President for Campaign Services (and former SUU star basketball player). Moreover, they learn that Tyson is considered “the real deal” — a bona fide NFL prospect whose statistics, performance, and moral character merit consideration for the Heisman Trophy. Finally, they are told that an anonymous donor has earmarked a \$100,000 contribution to SUU Athletics on the stipulation that it be used to promote Tyson Justice for the Heisman Trophy. Jim Naziam tells Excelsior employees that he expects their campaign plan to earn the bid from SUU Athletics to execute the campaign.

The semester begins with the players, who are now members of the campaign team, in possession of the ball at their own 20-yard line. To reach the end zone and score a touchdown, they must create an effective campaign — one that persuades national college football media voters to include Tyson Justice as one of three players they’re permitted to name on their Heisman Trophy ballots. The strategies

(curriculum) are designed to engage players as they cooperate on eight First Down assignments that will take them to the end zone. Each First Down assignment includes a Huddle, wherein participation in a focused discussion encourages collaboration. As part of each Huddle, players are divided into squads and tasked with specific duties that contribute to achievement of the First Down objectives. Once those duties are completed and submitted to the group, players reconvene in the Huddle to consider and critique one another's ideas and performance.

First Downs

The first module of the semester provides an overview of what goes into the individual steps of creating an effective sports public relations campaign plan. Subsequent modules and their accompanying assignments are designed to engage players in such a way that they cooperate and collaborate while putting what they learn in action. Here is a summary of the eight First Down assignments:

First Down 1 — Secondary Research.

Players begin this assignment by using the media resources provided in a Google Drive folder to become acquainted with Tyson Justice. These resources include newspaper and feature-length magazine articles, video highlights, radio interviews, podcasts, pages from the SUU football media guide, press releases, etc. After becoming familiar with the campaign, players conduct secondary research on the Heisman Trophy, its origins and history, when and how it is awarded, the process for selecting the winner and who is involved, selection criteria, etc. They seek and summarize academic research on issues such as voting trends and accompanying fluctuation, regional bias in voting patterns, and statistical probabilities in the three-tiered ballots cast by voters. When the secondary research is complete, players work in squads to write research summaries that serve as guidelines for articulating the goals and objectives of the campaign. Parts of these summaries are later repurposed for inclusion in the campaign plan.

First Down 2 — Goals and Objectives.

Guided in part by the research summaries written for the previous assignment and what they learn about formulating campaign goals and objectives, players collaborate to identify the campaign's specific goals and objectives. The primary goal — to execute a campaign that results in Tyson Justice winning the Heisman Trophy — tends to be obvious to most players. However, identifying and articulating secondary goals, the supporting objectives, and desired outcomes associated with each goal requires cooperative effort. The head coach engages players in this Huddle to help guide their efforts

to keep the campaign team from going down a rabbit hole that will sink the entire campaign from the outset.

First Down 3 — Stakeholders and Publics.

Guided by the goals and objectives articulated in the previous assignment and what they learn about identifying stakeholders and target publics, players collaborate to select the target audiences for campaign messages, both on a wide scale (stakeholders) and a more focused scale (publics). Each stakeholder group and its accompanying publics must be described in specific detail; justification of choices based on secondary research is required. At larger stages of the campaign, players sometimes realize they have failed to identify a key public at this stage. They are permitted to return to First Down 3 and add that public to the campaign plan, although doing so sometimes results in corresponding adjustments to subsequent First Down assignments.

First Down 4 — Key Messages and Channels.

Guided by secondary research, campaign goals and objectives, and target audiences, players collaborate to develop the key messages of the campaign. Then, based on what they have learned in class about public relations channels and tactics, they must select appropriate channels for communicating key messages. Appropriate channels often include direct-contact, indirect-contact, and non-traditional channels borrowed from marketing. As with First Down 3, players sometimes realize later in the campaign that they have failed to identify key messages or channels at this stage. They are permitted to return to First Down 4 to reconsider and/or add key messages or channels. Again, sometimes this requires additional work in subsequent steps, especially budgeting.

First Down 5 — Budget.

As noted previously, an anonymous donor has pledged up to \$100,000 to fund the campaign. The players understand that they may spend less, but they may not spend more. Also, they are informed that unused funds from the \$100,000 pledge will not be absorbed by the SUU Athletics Department budget. Therefore, they should not skimp on the campaign to reallocate funding for other department initiatives. In this assignment, players work together to prioritize messages and channels, setting a realistic budget with detailed descriptions of cost breakdowns required to execute the campaign. An effective budget includes realistic cost estimates for human resources, primary research activities (surveying or focus groups), delivery of key messages through mediated channels, other public relations tactics, and materials/supplies.

First Down 6 — Strategies and Tactics.

This step is easily the one the players enjoy the

most. It engages them in collaborative learning and cooperative formulation of the creative ideas that serve as the meat of the campaign —the proposed strategies and tactics designed to achieve each objective and attain the overall goal. In this assignment, students work together to produce message exemplars for a wide-ranging gamut of mediated and non-mediated channels. These exemplars are described in detail in the campaign plan itself and are provided as part of an appendix.

First Down 7 — Crisis Plan.

Because this is a course in sports public relations, the players are exposed to the importance of crisis communication. In this assignment, they tasked with working together to develop a crisis plan to be activated in case of an unexpected situation or occurrence that could significantly damage Tyson Justice's credibility and candidacy for the Heisman Trophy. After the plan is complete, the head coach springs an unexpected surprise on the students in the form of a TMZ Sports report about Tyson Justice that has the potential to explode into a full-blown crisis for the campaign. The players work together to activate the crisis plan and deal with the simulated crisis. The crisis plan itself is later included in the campaign plan.

First Down 8 — Campaign Plan.

Near the end of the semester, the players work together to create a campaign plan that includes edited or repurposed content from the previous seven First Down assignments. The campaign plan must demonstrate familiarity with Tyson Justice; understanding of Heisman Trophy tradition, history, and selection process/criteria; campaign goals and objectives; identification of stakeholders and target publics; key messages and channels; thorough description of strategies and tactics, accompanied the exemplars; a crisis plan and how it would be executed, if needed; specific steps and a sequential timeline with target dates for executing the campaign and accomplishing each objective; and specific, measurable criteria for evaluating whether the campaign was effective and achieved its goals. When the campaign plan is complete and perfected, it is converted to a PDF file and shared with the players so that they have something for their portfolios. The campaign plan bears the name of each team member. In the future, when prospective employers ask, "Have you ever worked on a sports public relations campaign?" players will be able to share the Touchdown Project campaign plan with pride and confidence.

Huddle Up!

Each First Down assignment includes a Huddle, convened in a Canvas discussion forum created specifically for that assignment. With a First Down assignment pending, players report to the Huddle early in the week. One of the players is designated to serve as the quarterback; he/she/they is/are responsible for leading the discussion, in consultation with the head coach. The head coach engages the quarterback in individual instruction before the Huddle and is present during the Huddle to comment or offer advice as needed. However, it is clear to the players that the quarterback cannot be expected to carry the ball without blocking. All players must contribute to the Huddle; part of the statistics (assessment) includes depth and quality of participation in the Huddle.

Unlike an actual football huddle, the quarterback is not the only person permitted to speak in the Huddle. Cooperate and collaboration are critical as players engage one another and exchange ideas. In most cases, after the initial Huddle dialogue, the quarterback "calls the play" by assigning players to smaller groups known as squads and assigning each squad to fulfill specific responsibilities associated with the First Down assignment. Squads and responsibilities are generally assigned in consultation with the head coach, but the quarterback actually calls the play in the Huddle. Each player is then responsible to work with the other members of his/her/their squad to contribute to the First Down assignment. After each squad fulfills its responsibilities, the results are posted in the Huddle forum, and players return to the Huddle for additional discussion and revision. Consensus is achieved when all players agree that the overall First Down assignment is complete.

Quarterback responsibilities are rotated to provide leadership opportunities to as many students as possible. Also, by consulting with the quarterback before the play is called, the head coach tries to ensure that players are assigned to work with different teammates, emulating conditions in a real-world sports public relations agency.

Typical Results

In general, most groups create an excellent campaign plan, beginning with detail summaries introducing Tyson Justice and describing the Heisman Trophy, its origins and history, when and how it is awarded, the process for selecting the winner and who is involved, selection criteria, etc.

Typical goals and objectives include the following:

Goal 1 – To execute a public relations campaign that results in Southern Utah quarterback Tyson Justice winning the 2023 Heisman Trophy.

Objective 1a – To promote Tyson Justice as a legitimate candidate deserving of the Heisman Trophy to the national sports news media, especially those members of the media who cast Heisman Trophy ballots.

Objective 1b – To create awareness among past Heisman Trophy winners of Tyson Justice as a quality football player and as a man of character and integrity.

Goal 2 – To promote SUU football as a national college football brand.

Objective 2a – To create awareness among influential people in college football that SUU is a quality program that should be considered on the same level as other top FCS schools.

Objective 2b – To dispel regional bias toward Tyson Justice, FCS football, and the Western Athletic Conference among national media representatives, Heisman Trophy voters, and other college football opinion leaders.

Typical stakeholders and publics include the following:

Stakeholders, Objective 1a – The national sports news media who cover or otherwise publicize college football. These people are opinion leaders in the sports world whose coverage and commentary will influence which players are considered as legitimate candidates for the Heisman Trophy.

Target Public – Members of the national sports news media who cover or otherwise publicize college football and cast Heisman Trophy ballots.

Stakeholders, Objective 1b – Opinion leaders who do not work in the sports news media but nevertheless influence public attitudes and views regarding college football. These individuals have clout; when they talk people listen.

Target Public – Former Heisman Trophy winners, especially those who have expressed concern about the shame and embarrassment that have tarnished the award based on the actions of Heisman recipients in the relatively recent past.

Stakeholders, Objective 2a – Opinion leaders in the sports news media and others who influence public attitudes and views regarding college football.

Target Publics – National sports news media who cover college football and vote in the weekly Associated Press Top

25 poll during the regular season; and members of the American Football Coaches Association who vote in the weekly FCS national coaches poll during the regular season.

Stakeholders, Objective 2b – National sports news media and college football opinion leaders in the Northeast, Mid-Atlantic, Midwest, South, and Southwest regions.

Target Public – All Heisman Trophy voters in the Northeast, Mid-Atlantic, Midwest, South, and Southwest regions.

Typical key messages and channels include the following:

Key Messages, Objective 1a

- Tyson Justice is one of the most effective college football players in the country; he performs at an elite level on the field each week.
- Tyson Justice is a catalyst for team success based on his exemplary performance on the field and leadership on and off the field.
- Tyson Justice's superior skills are reflected in his statistics, which compare favorably with the statistics of previous Heisman winners.

Channels

- Direct-contact: Organizational media (media guide, media day, personal and media interviews, photo ops, SUU Athletics website with blog)
- Direct-contact: Social media (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube)
- Indirect-contact: Broadcast and electronic media (radio/TV interviews, highlight packages, podcasts)
- Non-traditional contact (guerrilla marketing, newsjacking)

Key Messages, Objective 1b

- In addition to his superior athletic performance, Tyson Justice embodies the personal traits and characteristics that make him an ideal Heisman Trophy candidate, including the following:
 - » He is an exemplary leader who places the interests of his team and teammates ahead of his own.
 - » He represents commitment to SUU, his family, and his religious faith through his words and actions.
 - » He is a kind, humble, pleasant individual who demonstrates respect and concern for other people.
 - » He is committed to social justice and racial equality, using his national platform as a standout athlete to encourage meaningful change.
 - » He reflects the values of the Heisman Trust in such a way that he will be a model ambassador for college football

in the future, perpetuating the tradition established by previous Heisman winners.

Channels

- Direct-contact: Organizational media (personal and media interviews, photo ops, SUU Athletics website with blog)
- Direct-contact: Social media (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube)
- Indirect-contact: Broadcast and electronic media (radio/TV interviews, highlight packages, podcasts)
- Non-traditional contact (Partnership/brand ambassadorship, Stand for Something, newsjacking)

Key Message, Objective 2a

- SUU is a formidable football team and program that features skilled players who can compete at the national college level.

Channels

- Direct-contact: Social media (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube)
- Indirect-contact: Broadcast and electronic media (radio/TV interviews, highlight packages, podcasts)
- Non-traditional contact (guerrilla marketing, newsjacking)

Key Messages, Objective 2b

- The quality of competition in FCS football and in the Western Athletic Conference is such that SUU football consideration on both regional and national levels.
- As one of the best players in the history of FCS football and the Western Athletic Conference, Tyson Justice merits consideration on both regional and national levels. As such, he has earned serious consideration as a Heisman Trophy candidate.

Channels

- Direct-contact: Social media (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube)
- Indirect-contact: Broadcast and electronic media (radio/TV interviews, highlight packages, podcasts)
- Non-traditional contact (Partnership/brand ambassadorship, guerrilla marketing, newsjacking)

Typical strategies and tactics for all goals and objectives include the following:

- Social media campaign featuring a carefully planned message calendar for Twitter, Tik Tok, YouTube, Instagram, and Facebook
- Organizational media, including an abbreviated media guide focusing on Tyson Justice's candidacy for the Heisman Trophy; a proposed media day or media event, accompanied by a media kit; ideas for proposed photo ops; and a website accompanied by a blog (purported to be written by Tyson Justice but in reality,

ghost-written by a member of the SUU Athletics marketing staff)

- Earned media content achieved through personal contact with print, broadcast, electronic, and online media, including stories, feature-length articles, interviews, highlight packages, podcasts, blogs, etc.
- Partnership/brand ambassadorship achieved through an NIL agreement with an appropriate sponsor who will, in turn, provide additional free publicity and earned media content to promote Tyson Justice for the Heisman Trophy
- "Stand for Something" social-issues campaign in which Tyson Justice speaks out against sexual assault on college campuses, particularly in cases where intercollegiate athletes are accused perpetrators
- Newsjacking through monitoring of live sports news as it unfolds and spotting opportunities to hijack the story by inserting Tyson Justice at the center of subsequent conversations through expert commentary and social media messages
- Guerrilla marketing to increase awareness of Tyson Justice's brand through unconventional marketing strategies that add to an existing urban/sports environment and attract attention by their mere presence

Perhaps the best example of the latter tactic came from a group that proposed waiting for Tyson Justice to have a particularly outstanding performance, going to the site of ESPN's College Game Day broadcast the following Saturday, and setting up a larger-than-life mannequin dressed to look like Tyson and posed in the manner of the Heisman Trophy near the Game Day set. The obvious goal is to attract the attention and notice of both the Game Day broadcasters/producers and targeted stakeholders and publics. Other than a few tweets to get the ball rolling from contrived Twitter fan accounts, the campaign and SUU Athletics marketing staff remain silent on the stunt until after it has become national news.

Limits

Whether the Touchdown Project is an effective learning vehicle usually hinges on two factors.

First, the "buy-in" of learners is a critical factor. In one case in particular, students seemed to lack the motivation or willingness to participate whole-heartedly in the term project. No amount of instructor enthusiasm, solicitation of student input or feedback, or big-picture illustration of the project's potential benefits proved effective in getting this particular team off the bench and into the game. So-called "Come-to-Jesus" conversations, individually or collectively, were equally ineffective. This group was not interested

in doing anything more than mediocre to below-average work. Midway through the semester, the Touchdown Project was converted into an individual project, with predictably below-average results.

Second, the number of learners enrolled in the course has can affect how well the assignment fulfills its purpose. The ideal class size is 12 students. This is a manageable number of students that allows two-thirds of the class leadership opportunities as quarterback of one of the Huddles. (The remaining one-third of the class is assigned leadership duties in terms of writing, editing, and designing the campaign plan or overseeing the presentation to the client.) A class of 12 students also allows for parts of First Down assignments to be delegated to four squads of three players each or three squads of four players each. Obviously, classes of 10 to 14 students are manageable, but 12 is the ideal number. In larger classes (20 to 24 students), we have two campaign teams, which actually becomes more fun because the teams compete with each other and play their cards close to the vest in terms of identifying goals, objectives, stakeholders, publics, key messages, channels, strategies, and tactics.

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